

MIYAWAKI TECHNIQUE OF AFFORESTATION

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Received: May 14, 2021; *Accepted:* Sep 20, 2021

Introduction

Forest formation might take many more years in a natural manner. In the last two decades, scientists all around the world have gained fresh insights into both theoretical and practical approaches to natural ecosystem restoration and reconstruction (Clewel *et al.*, 2007). Miyawaki is a method developed by Japanese botanist Akira Miyawaki that aids in the rapid growth of thick, natural forests. The process includes mulching to improve soil fertility, as well as identifying and planting native trees in the area. Mulching was recommended to avoid soil dryness, erosion on steep slopes, weed development, shield seedlings from cold, and serve as manure when materials degrade (Miyawaki *et al.*, 2004). All intermediate and late successional species, as well as several companion species, were blended and extensively planted using this strategy (Miyawaki *et al.*, 1998). The dense planting resulted in a state of dynamic balance and cooperation among the many species (Padilla *et al.*, 2006). The method is expected to produce 10 times quicker plant growth and a plantation that is 30 times denser than typical. In ecologically damaged territories as well as urban environments, the Miyawaki approach has been used in Japan, South American nations, the Far East, and Malaysia. More urban woods were established in a shorter period of time. The benefits of urban woods are numerous, including reduced temperature, improved air quality, CO₂ sequestration, improved wellbeing indices, and a rise in real estate prices. To entice more clientele, numerous urban real estate developers are offering green projects in metro areas.

Main features of Miyawaki method

- Plantations are 30 times denser than traditional plantations.
- In the same region, at least 50-100 distinct natural species are planted.
- Improved noise and dust reduction by 30 times
- Carbon dioxide absorption is 30 times more than monoculture plantations.
- Annual growth of at least 1 metre is guaranteed.
- After the first three years, a totally maintenance-free, untamed, and natural forest.
- A forest that is totally free of chemical fertilisers and nourishes local wildlife.

Miyawaki method works in six steps

1. Begin with the soil. To determine what nutrients the soil is deficient in.
2. Determine which species should grow in this soil based on the climate.
3. Then, to provide the soil with whatever nutrients it requires, identify locally plentiful biomass accessible in that location. It's usually an agricultural or industrial by-product, but it can be nearly anything, and it has to come from within 50 kilometres of the location, so we have to be flexible.
4. Plant saplings that are up to 80 cm high, 3 to 5 saplings per square metre, once the soil has been modified to a depth of one metre.
5. The forest itself must be at least 100 square metres in size. After eight months, the forest has grown so dense that sunlight cannot reach the ground. Every drop of rain that falls is saved at this point, and every leaf that falls is transformed into humus. The more the forest expands, the more nutrients it produces for itself, allowing it to expand even faster. Individual trees begin to compete for sunlight as a result of this density, which is another reason why these forests develop so quickly.
6. For the first two or three years, the forest has to be watered and weeded, after which it becomes self-sustaining. After then, it's ideal to leave the forest as undisturbed as possible so that its ecology, including animals, can settle in.

Fig. 1: Steps to be followed in Miyawaki method.

Miyawaki in India

This strategy is steadily gaining traction in India. Afforest, a social company, collaborated with a variety of businesses and people to establish these forests. They recently collaborated with the Government of India's Department of Biotechnology (DBT) to transform a sewage-infested plot of land near the Barapullah drain. The drain was cleaned as part of a larger initiative called Local Treatment of Urban Sewage Streams for Healthy Reuse (LOTUS HR). DBT, the Ministry of Science and Technology, and the Government of India collaborated to build a demonstration facility to clean up the Barapullah drain. The foundation of the forest was set in July 2018 after early site inspections in January 2018.

Fig. 2: A forest created by Miyawaki method.

Conclusion

Every year, forests absorb around 2.6 billion tonnes of carbon dioxide, accounting for one-third of the CO₂ emitted by burning fossil fuels. Preventing timber logging, deforestation, and illegal poaching are critical methods for combatting climate change and mitigation. Growing trees and balancing biodiversity are both part of the ecological landscape restoration process. Landscape restoration may result in the sequestration of 3 to 4.3 billion tonnes of above-ground carbon by 2040, according to WRI India's Restoration Opportunities Atlas, which covers approximately 140 million hectares. In order to address climate change challenges, India's current forest acreage needs to be increased to 25 to 30 Mha. As a result, new inventive ways may be able to create more green cover in a shorter amount of time. Upscaling of these strategies requires cooperation from public and private institutions, as well as environmentalists.

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